

A PHANTOM-NODE-BASED COHESIVE ELEMENT FORMULATION WITH COUPLED PLASTICITY FOR THE SIMULATION OF ADHESIVE JOINTS

Carlos Sarrado¹, Joris J.C. Remmers² and Albert Turon¹

¹ AMADE, University of Girona
Campus Montilivi s/n, 17071 Girona (Spain)
carlos.sarrado@udg.edu | albert.turon@udg.edu, web page: <http://amade.udg.edu>

² Eindhoven University of Technology
PB 513, 5600 MB Eindhoven (The Netherlands)
j.j.c.remmers@tue.nl

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ABSTRACT

A new cohesive element for the simulation of adhesive joints based on the phantom node method is presented. A discontinuity crosses the element following a predefined path on its midplane and divides it into two independent subdomains. The continuum on either side of the crack has its own displacement field and is integrated independently, and so is the interface. Two coupled material models are used: a cohesive zone model for the interface and an elastoplastic model for the continuum, which has been formulated as an associated plastic model with isotropic hardening based on the Drucker-Prager yield criterion. The parameters required by the two models can be determined experimentally. Since the cohesive and continuum models are contained in the same element, they can be set to interact with each other. This yields an element with coupled plasticity and fracture that allows the detailed simulation of adhesive joints by means of a single interface element across the adhesive thickness. The formulation has been implemented as a user element subroutine in Abaqus 6.13 and post-processed in Paraview.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cohesive elements are an excellent approach for modelling damage evolution within predefined adhesive interfaces in a finite element analysis framework. They are able to reproduce the Fracture Process Zone (FPZ) ahead of a crack tip and accurately predict the fracture behaviour of adhesive joints.

In order to consistently account for the adhesive layer thickness in mixed-mode adhesive joints fracture, Sarrado et al. [1] proposed a finite-thickness cohesive element where the physical moduli of the adhesive and the interface penalty stiffness were decoupled. The resulting element was a combination of a zero-thickness interface embedded within a linear elastic material. With that approach, correct energy dissipation under mixed mode was ensured [2,3] and, at the same time, the actual physical properties of the adhesive could be used. However, the finite-thickness cohesive element proposed in [1] had the integration of a conventional cohesive element, which means that a single stress state is allowed through the thickness of the element. That would cause the element response to have snapback behaviour for element thicknesses greater than a certain value.

In the present work, the previous issue is overcome by proposing a new cohesive element based on the phantom node method [4]. A discontinuity crosses the element following a predefined path on its midplane and divides it into two independent subdomains. The continuum on either side of the crack has its own displacement field and is integrated independently, and so is the interface. Therefore, the stress states of the interface and each solid subelement are independent and the restriction on the element thickness to avoid the snapback behaviour is suppressed. In addition, all the stress components are available in the continuum part of the resulting element, unlike the conventional cohesive elements that can only account for the interface cohesive tractions.

2 ELEMENT FORMULATION AND IMPLEMENTATION

The proposed cohesive element is based on the cohesive band model [5]. It consists of two coupled material models: a cohesive zone model for the interface, which is based on the formulation proposed by Turon et al. [6], and an elastoplastic model for the continuum, which has been formulated in the present work as an associated plastic model with isotropic hardening based on the Drucker-Prager yield criterion [7].

The formulation presented in this section has been implemented in Abaqus 6.13 as a user element subroutine. The 3-dimensional version of the formulation is given in this section, although the element has been also implemented as a 2-dimensional plane stress and plane strain element.

2.1 Element kinematics

The formulation outlined in this subsection is an adaptation to a 3D elastoplastic cohesive element of the phantom node formulation proposed by van der Meer and Sluys [8].

In the finite element depicted in Figure 1, a discontinuity crosses the element at its horizontal midplane Γ_C , dividing it into two subelements denoted by A and B . The discontinuity in the displacement field of the element is created by adding a phantom node on top of each element node, which in practice is achieved by doubling the degrees of freedom of each node. In Figure 1, element A connects the four upper real nodes with the four lower phantom nodes, whereas element B connects the four lower real nodes with the four upper phantom nodes. This results in two independent and partially active overlapping elements.

Figure 1: Schematic 2-dimensional representation of the phantom-node-based cohesive element.

Consider \mathbf{u}^* as the nodal displacements vector given by the finite element software Abaqus, containing the displacement of both the real and the phantom degrees of freedom of each node. The decoupling matrices \mathbf{H}_A and \mathbf{H}_B are defined so that the nodal displacements of subelements A and B are obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_A &= \mathbf{H}_A \mathbf{u}^* \\ \mathbf{u}_B &= \mathbf{H}_B \mathbf{u}^* \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

\mathbf{H}_A and \mathbf{H}_B are operators that contain a one at the position (i, j) if the j -th position of \mathbf{u}^* corresponds to the i -th degree of freedom of \mathbf{u}_A or \mathbf{u}_B , respectively, or a zero otherwise. The element displacement field can be computed as

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{u}_A, & \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_A \\ \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{u}_B, & \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_B \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{x} is the coordinate vector of a point in the element and $\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x})$ is the element shape functions matrix, constructed as

$$\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{bmatrix} N_1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & N_8 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & N_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & N_8 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N_1 & \dots & 0 & 0 & N_8 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The following linear shape functions are defined:

$$N_i = \frac{1}{8}(1 + \xi\xi_i)(1 + \eta\eta_i)(1 + \mu\mu_i), \quad i = 1 \dots 8 \quad (4)$$

where ξ , η and μ are the element isoparametric coordinates and the subscript i refers to each node in the element.

The element strain field is computed from the displacement field as

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \varepsilon_{zz} \\ \varepsilon_{xy} \\ \varepsilon_{xz} \\ \varepsilon_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (5)$$

where the operator \mathbf{L} is defined as

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Given that each subelement has an independent displacement field, a different strain nodal displacement matrix is defined:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{B}_A(\mathbf{x}) &= \mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{H}_A \\ \mathbf{B}_B(\mathbf{x}) &= \mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{H}_B \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

so the strain field of the element reads

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{B}_A \cdot \mathbf{u}^*, & \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_A \\ \mathbf{B}_B \cdot \mathbf{u}^*, & \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_B \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

According to the weak form derivation presented in [8], the contribution of both overlapping elements to the element internal force vector, \mathbf{f} , is the sum of the contributions of the bulk adhesive, \mathbf{f}^{bulk} , and the cohesive interface, \mathbf{f}^{coh} :

$$\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{f}^{bulk} + \mathbf{f}^{coh} \quad (10)$$

The contribution to the element internal forces of the bulk is obtained directly from the nodal displacements vector as

$$\mathbf{f}^{bulk} = \mathbf{K}^{bulk} \cdot \mathbf{u}^* \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{K}^{bulk} is the bulk contribution to the element stiffness matrix, computed as

$$\mathbf{K}^{bulk} = \begin{cases} \int_{\Omega_A} \mathbf{B}_A^T \cdot \mathbf{D}^{bulk} \cdot \mathbf{B}_A \, d\Omega, & \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_A \\ \int_{\Omega_B} \mathbf{B}_B^T \cdot \mathbf{D}^{bulk} \cdot \mathbf{B}_B \, d\Omega, & \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_B \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{D}^{bulk} is the continuum constitutive law presented in Section 2.2. Note that the integration in the previous equation is performed only in the active part of each subelement.

The contribution to the element internal forces of the cohesive interface is obtained as

$$\mathbf{f}^{coh} = \mathbf{H}_A^T \cdot \mathbf{f}_A^{coh} + \mathbf{H}_B^T \cdot \mathbf{f}_B^{coh} \quad (13)$$

where

$$\mathbf{f}_A^{coh} = -\mathbf{f}_B^{coh} = \int_{\Gamma_c} \mathbf{N}^T(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}(\boldsymbol{\Delta}) \, d\Gamma \quad (14)$$

$\boldsymbol{\tau}(\boldsymbol{\Delta})$ is the cohesive constitutive law presented in Section 2.3 that relates the interface displacement jumps, $\boldsymbol{\Delta}$, to the cohesive tractions, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$. The interface displacement jump is obtained as

$$\boldsymbol{\Delta}(x, y) = \mathbf{N}(x) \cdot (\mathbf{H}_A - \mathbf{H}_B) \cdot \mathbf{u}^* \quad (15)$$

The contribution of the cohesive interface to the element stiffness matrix therefore is

$$\mathbf{K}^{coh} = (\mathbf{H}_A^T - \mathbf{H}_B^T) \int_{\Gamma_c} \mathbf{N}^T(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}(\boldsymbol{\Delta}) \cdot \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x}) \, d\Gamma \cdot (\mathbf{H}_A - \mathbf{H}_B) \quad (16)$$

2.2 Continuum elastoplastic constitutive model

An associated plastic model with isotropic hardening based on the Drucker-Prager yield criterion has been formulated for the bulk adhesive. The stresses in the continuum are computed as

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}(\varepsilon_{kl} - \varepsilon_{kl}^P) \quad (17)$$

where C_{ijkl} is the elastic constitutive tensor, ε_{kl} is the total strain tensor – i.e. the sum of elastic and plastic strains – and ε_{kl}^P is the plastic strain tensor.

The yield surface f is defined as

$$f = F(s_{ij}, \sigma_{kk}) - \xi(\alpha) \leq 0 \quad (18)$$

where $F(s_{ij}, \sigma_{kk})$ is the yield criterion and $\xi(\alpha)$ is the hardening function. The following Drucker-Prager yield criterion has been used:

$$F = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}s_{ij}s_{ji} + \eta\sigma_{kk}} - k \quad (19)$$

where s_{ij} is the deviatoric stress tensor and η and k are material parameters that can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} k &= \sigma_y^{sh} \\ \eta &= \frac{\sigma_y^{sh}}{\sigma_y^T} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where σ_y^T and σ_y^{sh} are the tensile and shear yield stresses of the adhesive under pure uniaxial and shear loads, respectively.

The isotropic hardening function is defined as

$$\xi(\alpha) = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} + \eta\right)^2 \frac{E_{adh} \cdot m}{1 - m} \alpha \quad (21)$$

where E_{adh} is the Young modulus of the adhesive, α is the plasticity variable and m is the relationship between the plastic and elastic moduli of the adhesive under uniaxial tensile loads. Therefore, m is a material parameter that can range from 0 (perfect plasticity) to 1 (elastic material).

The evolution of the internal variables with respect to the scalar plasticity variable needs to be defined for the model to be integrable. In an associated plastic model, the plastic flow must be normal to the yield surface, so the following flow rule is obtained:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^P = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{s_{ij}}{\sqrt{s_{ij}s_{ji}}} + \eta\delta_{ij}\right) \dot{\alpha} \quad (22)$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta.

When $f < 0$, the material point is in an elastic regime. If $f > 0$, equilibrium is not reached and the yield surface is expanded until $f = 0$. The increase in the plasticity variable is found by means of a Newton-Raphson iterative procedure and the evolution of the other six internal variables is obtained using the flow rule.

For the convergence of the implicit non-linear finite element algorithm, the tangent constitutive tensor is computed as

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}}{\partial \varepsilon_{pq}} = C_{ijkl} \left[\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} - \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{s_{kl}}{\sqrt{s_{kl} s_{lk}}} + \eta \delta_{kl} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{\sqrt{2} \cdot G \cdot \frac{s_{pq}}{\sqrt{s_{pq} s_{qp}}} + \eta \cdot \frac{G_{adh} \cdot E_{adh}}{3G_{adh} - E_{adh}} \delta_{pq}}{G + 3\eta^2 \cdot \frac{G_{adh} \cdot E_{adh}}{3G_{adh} - E_{adh}} + \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} + \eta \right)^2 \frac{E_{adh} \cdot m}{1 - m}} \right) \right] \quad (23)$$

where G_{adh} is the adhesive shear modulus.

2.3 Interface cohesive zone model

Turon et al. [2] showed that the following constraint between the interface properties must be fulfilled in order to guarantee non-negative energy dissipation when both the damage variable and the mixed-mode ratio change at the same time:

$$\frac{k_{sh}}{k_3} = \frac{G_{Ic}}{G_{sh,c}} \left(\frac{\tau_{sh}^0}{\tau_3^0} \right)^2 \quad (24)$$

where k_3 and k_{sh} are the opening and shear modes penalty stiffnesses, respectively, G_{Ic} and $G_{sh,c}$ are the opening and shear modes fracture toughnesses, respectively, and τ_3^0 and τ_{sh}^0 are the opening and shear modes interlaminar strengths, respectively. The fracture toughnesses and the interlaminar strengths are measurable material parameters, whereas the penalty stiffnesses are very high numerical parameters to ensure the bonding of the interface prior to damage. Turon et al. [6] proposed a mode-variable penalty stiffness cohesive zone model that internally adjusts one of the penalty stiffness to fulfill the energy dissipation constraint. The formulation in [6] has been used for the interface model in this work and is outlined next for the sake of completeness.

The interface constitutive equation reads

$$\tau_i = (1 - d)(K_{ij} \Delta_j + \delta_{i3} K_{33} \langle -\Delta_3 \rangle) \quad (25)$$

where d is a scalar damage variable and K_{ij} is the penalty stiffness matrix. K_{11} , K_{22} , K_{33} are the penalty stiffnesses for modes II, III and I, respectively, and are the only non-zero terms of the penalty stiffness matrix. The Macaulay brackets, defined as $\langle x \rangle = \frac{1}{2}(x + |x|)$, are used to avoid interpenetration under mode I compressive stresses.

The mixed-mode damage evolution law is defined from the mixed-mode norm of the cohesive tractions (τ) and of the displacements jump (λ). The mixed-mode traction is defined as the Euclidean norm of the components of the tractions vector, whereas the mixed-mode displacement jump is defined as

$$\lambda = \frac{K_{ii}^2 (\Delta_i^2 - \delta_{3i} \langle -\Delta_3 \rangle^2)}{\sqrt{K_{ii} (\Delta_i^2 - \delta_{3i} \langle -\Delta_3 \rangle^2)}} \quad (26)$$

The mode-dependent interface penalty stiffness K_B is

$$K_B = K_{33}(1 - B) + BK_{sh} \quad (27)$$

where B is the mixed-mode ratio, defined as

$$B = \frac{K_{11}\Delta_1^2 + K_{22}\Delta_2^2}{K_{11}\Delta_1^2 + K_{22}\Delta_2^2 + K_{33}(-\Delta_3)^2} \quad (28)$$

The mixed-mode damage activation function is defined as

$$g(\Delta_i) = h(\Delta_i) - r_d \leq 0 \quad (29)$$

where $h(\Delta_i)$ is a monotonic loading function and r_d is the damage threshold function. $h(\Delta_i)$ is defined as the ratio of energy dissipated during the damage process as

$$h(\Delta_i) = \min \left\{ \frac{\lambda - \Delta^o}{\Delta^f - \Delta^o}, 1 \right\} \quad (30)$$

and r_d is taken as the maximum value of $h(\Delta_i)$ over time until it reaches 1. Δ^o and Δ^f are the displacement jumps corresponding to the onset and propagation of damage, respectively. They are defined for mixed mode based on the Benzeggagh and Kenane [9] interpolation criterion, yielding

$$\Delta^o = \sqrt{\frac{K_{33}(\Delta_3^o)^2 + (K_{sh}(\Delta_{sh}^o)^2 - K_{33}(\Delta_3^o)^2)B^{\eta_c}}{K_B}} \quad (31)$$

$$\Delta^f = \frac{K_{33}\Delta_3^o\Delta_3^f + (K_{sh}\Delta_{sh}^o\Delta_{sh}^f - K_{33}\Delta_3^o\Delta_3^f)B^{\eta_c}}{K_B\Delta^o} \quad (32)$$

where η_c is the Benzeggagh-Kenane mixed-mode interpolation parameter, Δ_3^o and Δ_{sh}^o are the damage onset displacement jumps under pure opening and shear modes, respectively, and Δ_3^f and Δ_{sh}^f are the damage propagation displacement jumps under pure opening and shear modes, respectively. The pure-mode onset and propagation displacement jumps are obtained from

$$\Delta_3^o = \tau_3^o / K_{33} \quad (33)$$

$$\Delta_{sh}^o = \tau_{sh}^o / K_{11} \quad (34)$$

$$\Delta_3^f = 2\mathcal{G}_{Ic} / \tau_3^o \quad (35)$$

$$\Delta_{sh}^f = 2\mathcal{G}_{IIc} / \tau_{sh}^o \quad (36)$$

where \mathcal{G}_{Ic} and \mathcal{G}_{IIc} are the pure modes I and II fracture toughnesses, respectively, and τ_3^o and τ_{sh}^o are the pure mode I and II interlaminar strengths, respectively.

The tangent constitutive tensor is numerically computed by means of a linear perturbation method.

2.4 Constitutive models parameters

All the material parameters of the two constitutive models are experimentally measurable. They are outlined in Table 1, along with the test type required for measuring them. No further calibration is required. In addition to the parameters presented in Table 1, two numerical penalty stiffnesses are required for the cohesive model. One is set to be 10^6 and the other is computed to fulfil the constraint given by Equation (24).

	Parameter	Test type
<i>Continuum elastoplastic model</i>	E_{adh}	1. Bulk adhesive tensile test
	ν_{adh}	1. Bulk adhesive tensile test
	σ_y^T	1. Bulk adhesive tensile test
	m	1. Bulk adhesive tensile test
	σ_y^{sh}	2. Bulk adhesive shear test
<i>Interface cohesive model</i>	G_{Ic}	3. Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness test
	G_{IIc}	4. Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness test
	τ_3^0	1. Bulk adhesive tensile test
	τ_{sh}^0	2. Bulk adhesive shear test
	η_c	5. Mixed mode interlaminar fracture toughness tests

Table 1: Measurement of required material parameters.

3 MODEL VALIDATION

The presented model has been validated by means of the simulation of fracture mechanics tests. The results were extracted from Abaqus and post-processed in Paraview. A Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) test was simulated using the 2-dimensional plane-stress formulation of the proposed element for modelling the interface. The contribution of both elastic and plastic strains to the total vertical strain of the adhesive is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Adhesive elastic, plastic and total vertical strains during crack growth in a DCB test.

The results shown in Figure 2 are consistent with the expected response. As the interface is undergoing monotonic loading prior to damage, its plastic deformation also grows monotonically until the damage threshold is reached. After that, the plastic strain of the interface remains constant as it damages and gets progressively unloaded.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A new cohesive element has been proposed that allows the detailed simulation of adhesive interfaces by capturing both its elastoplastic and fracture behaviour. The proposed element is based on the phantom-node method. The continuum part of the element has an associated plastic model with isotropic hardening based on the Drucker-Prager yield criterion. This continuum is crossed by a discontinuity in its midplane, whose behaviour is governed by a cohesive zone model. The main advantage of the proposed approach is that the two material models can be coupled. The new element has been implemented in Abaqus 6.13 as a user element subroutine and post-processed in Paraview. A validation example has been presented that helps validate the accuracy of the approach, even though it does not take advantage of the coupling between the two material models.

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